

CATALYST DEVELOPMENT FOR ACETYLENE CATALYTIC HYDROGENATION SYNTHESIS USING "WET" AND SUSPENSION METHODS

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Abstract. Among the sorbents used in adsorption processes and catalysis, zeolites stand out for their acid resistance, thermal stability, and acidic properties. Acid treatment and activation are carried out in a reactor equipped with a mechanical stirrer. The calculated amount of high-silica zeolite (HSZ) is directed into the reactor (1), and a certain amount of 10% sulfuric acid is added at the same location. The use of new high-performance nanocatalysts improves the environmental characteristics of industrial processes and technologies, reduces harmful emissions into the atmosphere, and facilitates the creation of environmentally friendly alternative energy resources, new products, and materials. Under the influence of this nanocatalyst, acetylene conversion reaches 90-97%, acetone yield is 96.2%, and acetaldehyde yield is 2.2%.

Keywords: acetone, water, acetylene, bentonite, HSZ (high-silica zeolite), catalyst, ball mill, vibro-sieve.

Introduction. Among the sorbents used in adsorption processes and catalysis, zeolites stand out for their acid resistance, thermal stability, and acidic properties. Zeolites are widely used in petrochemistry, the processing of petroleum, natural gas, and associated petroleum gases, the separation and purification of liquid and gaseous substances, as well as in sorbents and catalysts. Today, the main challenge in zeolite production is to reduce costs and simplify synthesis processes. To address this issue, scientific research has been conducted on the production of HSZs based on local raw materials (bentonite). Based on the findings, we selected a catalyst created using a suspension method that exhibits high activity, selectivity, and productivity, with strong thermal stability and targeted reactivity [1-2].

Research Results and Discussion. To synthesize acetone from acetylene, the catalyst preparation method was modified by adding various d-element salts as promoters. The catalyst was prepared using two methods: "wet" and suspension methods [80]. The catalyst composition consists of 5% ZnO, 5% Fe₂O₃, 5% Cr₂O₃, 3% MnO₂, and 1% V₂O₅. The catalyst production process includes the following main stages: acid treatment and activation of high-silica zeolite; mixing and shaping; and thermal processing of the catalyst. Figure 2.5 presents the technological scheme for the production of ZnO·Fe₂O₃·Cr₂O₃·MnO₂·V₂O₅/HSZ-based catalysts [3].

Acid treatment and activation take place in a reactor equipped with a mechanical stirrer. The calculated amount of HSZ is directed into the reactor (1), where a specific amount of 10% sulfuric acid is added. The components are stirred for 1 hour, washed, and then dried at 95°C for 3 hours (2).

Meanwhile, coal is ground in a mill (8). The mixture of components is directed to the mixer (11), where $\frac{3}{4}$ of the peptizer's aqueous solution is added under intense stirring (extraction phosphoric acid solution is used as the peptizer). Mixing continues until a homogeneous mass is obtained. The pre-prepared binding agent, after activation and drying, is ground in a mill (8) and sent to the mixer (11) to be blended with the remaining components, after which $\frac{1}{4}$ of the peptizer is added.

Figure 2.5. Technological Scheme for the Production of $ZnO \cdot Fe_2O_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3 \cdot MnO_2 \cdot V_2O_5$ / HSZ-based Catalyst

1 – Stirrer-activator; 2 – Hopper for HSZ; 3 – Container for 10% sulfuric acid; 4 – Drying oven; 5, 6, 7 – Containers for $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Cr(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$, and $Mn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$; 8 – Ball mill; 9, 10 – Containers for distilled water; 11 – Paddle mixer; 12 – Shaping machine; 13 – Conveyor dryer; 14 – Shaft furnace; 15 – Vibro-sieve.

The mixing process continues for 30–40 minutes, after which the mass is directed to the shaping machine (12). A screw-type shaping machine was chosen for this purpose, allowing for the formation of granules with a diameter of 6–8 mm and a length of 8–10 mm. The granules exiting the granulator retain 20–25% moisture content. The contact mass was dried in a drying unit (13) at $100 \pm 5^\circ C$ for 5 hours [4].

Thermal treatment of the catalyst is carried out in a rotary-type furnace (14), where the burning gases and raw material granules pass through the furnace in a counterflow manner. The initial calcination temperature is $200^\circ C$, and the temperature is increased by $50^\circ C$ every 30 minutes, reaching $450-500^\circ C$. After calcination, the catalyst is sieved using a vibro-sieve (15) and sent to the finished product warehouse [5].

The use of new high-performance nanocatalysts enhances the ecological characteristics of industrial processes and technologies, reduces harmful emissions into the atmosphere, and facilitates the development of environmentally friendly alternative energy sources, new products, and materials [6]. The active center of the nano-scale core material is zeolites, among which bentonite is one of the most prominent.

For the catalytic hydrogenation of acetylene, a catalyst was prepared using the precipitation method, utilizing aqueous solutions of $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Cr(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$, $Mn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, and $VO(NO_3)_3$ according to the scheme in Figure 2.6. The support material (carrier) was filtered, dried at $130^\circ C$, and calcined in a furnace at $800-1100^\circ C$ for 5 hours.

For catalyst preparation using the impregnation method, sodium silicate solution was first mixed with sulfuric acid in water [7]. The precipitate was filtered, dried at 130°C, and calcined at 800-1300°C. Then, aqueous solutions of $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Cr(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$, and $Mn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ were added. After 3 hours, the obtained catalyst was dried and calcined at 800-1300°C. Finally, the required amount of $VO(NO_3)_3$ solution was added to the mass. The catalyst was then filtered, dried, and calcined following the same sequence [8].

The high efficiency of nanocatalysts is associated with changes in charge, energy, mass transfer, and information transfer processes occurring in nanostructures during chemical reactions. The use of new high-performance nanocatalysts in industry improves the environmental properties of processes and technologies, reduces emissions, and contributes to the development of environmentally friendly alternative energy sources, new products, and materials [9].

The prospects for using catalysts with nanoparticles in catalysis are based on two key factors:

As particle size decreases, most atoms are located on the surface, increasing the specific surface area, making the catalyst highly active in heterogeneous reactions.

Many nanoparticle properties depend on size (size effect), meaning that adjusting the size allows control over both activity and selectivity. As catalyst particle size decreases, the reaction rate increases significantly.

Based on these findings, studying the application of nanocatalysts composed of Zn, Fe, Cr, Mn, and V metals and other multifunctional elements in the hydration reactions of acetylene and its derivatives is a pressing scientific task [10].

Figure 2.6. Schematic Diagram of $ZnO:Fe_2O_3:Cr_2O_3:MnO_2:V_2O_5/HSZ$ Nanoparticle Synthesis

Following the synthesis process, we examined the effect of the mass ratios of the active catalyst components on the catalytic activity in the catalytic hydrogenation of acetylene reaction.

The obtained results are presented in Table 2.20.

Table 2.20. The Effect of Mass Ratios of Active Catalyst Components on the Catalytic Activity in the Hydrogenation of Acetylene Reaction.

№	catalyst composition					Catalyst proficiency, g/l·kat·h
	Zn(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O Fe(NO ₃) ₃ ·6H ₂ O Cr(NO ₃) ₃ ·9H ₂ O Mn(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	Zn(NO ₃) ₂ ·6 H ₂ O mass, %	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ ·6 H ₂ O mass, %	Cr(NO ₃) ₃ ·9 H ₂ O mass, %	Mn(NO ₃) ₂ ·6 H ₂ O mass, %	
1	6:6:6:0.6	30	30	30	3	300
2	6:0:6:0	30	0	30	0	250
3	0:6:6:1	0	30	30	5	265
4	3:1:3:0.2	15	5	15	1	260
5	1:3:3:0.6	5	15	15	3	280
6	3:3:1:0.8	15	15	5	4	290
7	1:1:0:0.6	5	5	-	3	260
8	1:1:1:0.4	5	5	5	2	315
9	1:1:1:0.6	5	5	5	3	330
10	1:1:1:0.2	5	5	5	1	300
11	1:1:1	5	5	5	0	285

As seen from Table 2.25, the effect of the mass ratios of active catalyst components on the catalytic activity in the catalytic acetylation of acetylene reaction reaches its highest productivity when the mass ratios of Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O:Fe(NO₃)₃·6H₂O:Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O = 5:5:5:3 (in mass percentages).

The morphology of the catalysts was studied using wave electron microscopy (WEM) with a Vegall LMU (Czech Republic) device. Additionally, the porous structure was determined based on the analysis of adsorption curves obtained by nitrogen thermosorption. The specific surface area of the catalytic system (Ssol) was measured using the BET method, while the volume of micro- and mesopores was determined using the BJH method.

As observed in Table 2.21, the synthesized catalysts ensure a high acetylene conversion rate. However, their stability is 1 to 1.5 times lower compared to the zinc-iron-chromium-manganese-vanadium/HSZ catalyst.

A catalyst promoted with up to 1.0% V₂O₅ exhibits sufficient activity, mechanical strength, and stability. A catalyst containing 5% ZnO, 5% Fe₂O₃, 5% Cr₂O₃, and 3% MnO₂ ensures a high acetone yield. When the reaction is conducted at 300–500°C, the acetone yield reaches 96.2% relative to the reacted acetylene. Additional byproducts include acetaldehyde, 3-hydroxybutanal, crotonaldehyde, butanal, ethyl acetate, and paraldehyde.

During the promotion of catalysts prepared by the suspension method based on zinc-iron-chromium-manganese-vanadium/HSZ compounds, the formation of nitrate salts (Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Fe(NO₃)₃·6H₂O, Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, Mn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, and VO(NO₃)₃) was studied using X-ray diffraction analysis. The results indicate that these compounds contribute to an increase in catalyst activity.

In the presence of this nanocatalyst, the acetylene conversion reaches 90–97%, while the acetone yield is 96.2%, and the acetaldehyde yield is 2.2%.

Table 2.21. Composition and Properties of Synthesized Zinc-Iron-Chromium-Manganese-Vanadium/HSZ Catalysts ($T = 698-703$ K).

№	Catalyst composition, mass %	comparative surface area, m^2/g	Working time until regeneration, hours	Efficiency, g/kg, kat·h	Conversion of acetylene%
1	ZnO:Fe ₂ O ₃ /YuKS	230	150	180	56
2	ZnO:Cr ₂ O ₃ /YuKS	220	160	165	78
3	ZnO:Fe ₂ O ₃ :MnO ₂ /YuKS	135	195	190	80
4	ZnO:Cr ₂ O ₃ :MnO ₂ /YuKS	151	200	170	84
5	ZnO:Fe ₂ O ₃ :Cr ₂ O ₃ /YuKS	183	220	178	86
6	ZnO:Fe ₂ O ₃ :Cr ₂ O ₃ :MnO ₂ /YuKS	201	235	182	82
7	ZnO:Fe ₂ O ₃ :MnO ₂ :V ₂ O ₅ /YuKS	195	260	167	84
8	ZnO:Cr ₂ O ₃ :MnO ₂ :V ₂ O ₅ /YuKS	200	275	174	78
9	ZnO:Fe ₂ O ₃ :Cr ₂ O ₃ :MnO ₂ :V ₂ O ₅ /YuKS	203	300	230	97.2
10	ZnO:Co ₂ O ₃ :Cr ₂ O ₃ :MnO ₂ :V ₂ O ₅ /YuKS	185	270	192	87
11	ZnO:Co ₂ O ₃ :Cr ₂ O ₃ :Mn ₂ O ₃ :V ₂ O ₅ /YuKS	155	260	187	83
12	ZnO:Fe ₂ O ₃ :Cr ₂ O ₃ :Mn ₂ O ₃ :V ₂ O ₅ /YuKS	140	250	195	88

Conclusion. Using the "wet" and suspension methods, thermally stable, highly active, selective, and productive ZnO·Fe₂O₃·Cr₂O₃·MnO₂·V₂O₅/HSZ nanocatalysts were developed from local raw materials for the catalytic hydration of acetylene. The thermodynamics of the catalytic hydration of acetylene were justified. The kinetic laws of the catalytic hydration reactions were studied, and their reaction mechanisms were proposed. Additionally, additive kinetic equations describing the reaction processes were developed (with an average quadratic deviation of less than 3%).

For acetone synthesis via catalytic hydration of acetylene, the ZnO·Fe₂O₃·Cr₂O₃·MnO₂·V₂O₅/HSZ catalyst was successfully tested at "Navoiyazot" JSC and was recommended for industrial implementation.

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